

Malate Complexes of Lanthanum(III) and Cerium(III)

NIRADA KUMARI MOHANTY and R. K. PATNAIK

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engg. College, Rourkela-769008, Orissa

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Lanthanum(III) and Cerium(III) form neutral complexes with malic acid below pH 6.4 and 6.1 respectively. The equilibrium constants of the reaction $M^{3+} + H_2ML \rightleftharpoons C + 3H^+$ are 3.75×10^{-11} and 1.67×10^{-10} , for lanthanum and cerium malate complexes respectively. The equilibrium constants of the reaction $M^{3+} + ML^{-} \rightleftharpoons C + H^+$ are 1.57×10^{-9} and 2.05×10^{-9} for lanthanum and cerium malates respectively.

MALATE complexes of rare earths were studied potentiometrically by Jercan and Popa¹. Roulet *et al*² have also reported that malic, maleic and methyl succinic acids form 1:1 and 1:2 complexes with rare earths. This paper deals with the determination of the equilibrium constants on the formation of lanthanum and cerium malate complexes by pH metric method.

Experimental

pH titrations were carried out at $32 \pm 1^\circ$ under nitrogen atmosphere with the help of a Marconi pH meter (TF 1093/1) having an accuracy of 0.02 pH. La and Ce were estimated gravimetrically as oxides after precipitation as oxalates and subsequent ignition. Ionic strength of 0.1 M was maintained by adding suitable amount of KNO_3 solution. Since the reactions were slow, the solutions were stored in stoppered bottles for 24 hours, before the measurements of pH.

Fig. 1. pH titration of 50 ml of solution containing .003125 g. mole of malic acid and 0.035 g. mole of KNO_3 (curve A) and that of the same volume of two other solutions containing the same quantities of the above constituents and 0.00025 g. mole of lanthanum nitrate (curve B) and 0.00025 g. mole of cerium nitrate (curve B') against 0.1 N sodium hydroxide.

Results and Discussion

The proton liberation remains same when the metal to ligand ratio is increased from 1:1.25 to 1:5. This indicates the formation of a 1:1 type of complex in both cases of lanthanum and cerium.

The reaction in experiment 1 (Fig. 1) can be represented as

It can be shown as in cases of citrate complexes of cadmium³ and yttrium⁴ and tartrate complex of yttrium⁵ that,

$$\frac{\Delta[NaOH] - \frac{a}{b} \Delta[M]}{[C]} = n - a/b \quad (2)$$

when the formation of the complex is complete,

The values of n at different pH were calculated. It was less than 3, below pH 6.4 and 6.1 in cases of lanthanum and cerium respectively. Hence a neutral complex is formed with liberation of 3 protons below these pH values. The equilibrium constants (K) of the reactions (1) are found to be 4.18×10^{-11} , 2.89×10^{-11} , 3.78×10^{-11} , 3.69×10^{-11} and 4.26×10^{-11} at pH 5.6, 5.8, 6.0, 6.1 and 6.4 respectively for lanthanum and 1.58×10^{-10} , 2.07×10^{-10} , 1.67×10^{-10} and 1.36×10^{-10} at pH 4.4, 5.0, 5.2 and 5.8 respectively for cerium. The mean values of K were 3.75×10^{-11} and 1.67×10^{-10} for lanthanum and cerium respectively.

In experiment 2 (Fig. 2), the pH of both the systems decreases gradually due to the liberation of protons during complex formation. The pH of both the systems are less than 5 indicating the formation of a neutral complex as observed in the previous experiment. The

0.05(M) Sodium malate added in ml

Fig. 2. pH titration of 50 ml of solution containing 0.005 g. mole of KNO_3 (curve A) and same volume of two other solutions containing the same quantities of the above constituents and 0.00025 g. mole of lanthanum nitrate (curve B) and 0.00025 g. mole of cerium nitrate (curve B') against 0.05 M sodium malate.

formation of this complex will be complete at about the 1:1 inflection point. The reaction in this experiment can be represented as

$$K_3 = \frac{[\text{C}][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{M}^{3+}][\text{ML}^{2-}]} \quad (3-1)$$

Below the 1:1 equivalence point, it can be shown as in the tartrate complexes of manganese⁶ and yttrium⁶ and citrate complexes of cobalt⁷ and yttrium⁴ that

$$[\text{M}(\text{NO}_3)_3] = [\text{C}] + [\text{M}^{3+}]$$

$$[\text{ML}] = [\text{C}] + p[\text{HML}^-]$$

$$\text{where } p = 1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_1} + \frac{k_2}{[\text{H}^+]}$$

$$[\text{C}] = [\text{H}^+] + r[\text{HML}^-]$$

$$\text{where } r = 1 + 2 \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_1}$$

$$[\text{HML}^-] = \frac{[\text{ML}] - [\text{H}^+]}{r + p}$$

where $[\text{ML}]$, $[\text{HML}^-]$, $[\text{ML}^{2-}]$, $[\text{C}]$ and $[\text{M}^{3+}]$ are represented by the molar concentrations of total malate, bimalate, malate complex and metal ion (lanthanum or cerium ions) respectively. k_1 and k_2 are the dissociation constants of malic acid⁸ ($k_1 = 5.5 \times 10^{-4}$ and $k_2 = 2.1 \times 10^{-6}$)

K_3 values were calculated as before and are 1.27×10^{-8} , 2.21×10^{-8} , 1.43×10^{-8} and 1.39×10^{-8} at pH 5.0, 4.9, 4.8 and 4.7 respectively in case of lanthanum and 1.52×10^{-8} , 1.68×10^{-8} , 2.18×10^{-8} and 2.85×10^{-8} at pH 4.55, 4.5, 4.45 and 4.4 respectively in case of cerium system. The mean values are 1.57×10^{-8} and 2.05×10^{-8} for lanthanum and cerium respectively.

It can be shown that $K_3 \times k_1 \times k_2 = K$. The values of $K_3 \times k_1 \times k_2$ are 1.81×10^{-11} and 2.37×10^{-10} for lanthanum and cerium systems respectively which are exactly similar to the values of K obtained from experiment 1.

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